

PARENTAL STYLES AS PREDICATORS OF CALLOUS- UNEMOTIONAL TRAITS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AWKA, ANAMBRA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined parental styles as predictors of callous-unemotional traits among secondary school students in Awka, Anambra State. The study used 286 secondary school students in Awka, Anambra State, comprising 131(45.8%) males and 155(54.2%) females aged from 14 to 18 years with mean age of 15.29 and a standard deviation of 1.46. Simple random sampling method was utilized in selecting the class and schools and purposive sampling method was employed to recruit participants. Instruments used in this study were the parental authority questionnaire which measures parenting styles, inventory of callous-unemotional traits which measures the callous-unemotional traits. Predictive design was employed for this study and Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected. The study revealed authoritative parenting style positively and significantly predicted callous unemotional traits at (F3, 282) $\beta = .47$, $t = 9.73$, $p < .01$, conversely, authoritarian parenting style negatively predict

callous unemotional traits at (F3, 282) $\beta = -.23$, $t = -4.92$, $p < .01$, and permissive parenting style

negatively predicted callous unemotional traits at (F3, 282) $\beta = -.66$, $t = -13.17$, $p < .01$. Based on

the findings, the study recommended that parents, and teachers should assist in personality

assessment and psychoeducation of students.

Keywords: Parenting styles, Callous-Unemotional traits. Secondary school, students

INTRODUCTION

School is a place of learning, growth, and, hopefully, joy. But for some, it can also be a source of immense stress and anxiety, casting a long shadow over students' mental health. The constant worry about grades, tests, and college applications can trigger feelings of inadequacy and failure. More so, students are often confused about how to deal with academic pressure which often squeezes the joy of learning out of them. This, in turn, can fuel anxiety and depression, making it difficult to focus, sleep, or even enjoy hobbies and social struggles that leads to callous-unemotional (CU) which is typified marked by deficiency in empathy, a pronounced lack of guilt, and a shallow or restricted emotional affect, are not merely behavioural quirks but harbingers of serious psychological concerns (Nweke et al., 2019, Onyemaechi, 2025. Okonkwo, et al., 2023; Anazonwu, et al., 2016; Waller et al., 2020). Interestingly, traits are intricately linked with severe antisocial behaviours and serve as precursors to psychopathy, painting a troubling picture of future behavioural patterns if left unaddressed.

Callous-unemotional (CU) traits, characterized by diminished empathy, guilt, and restricted affect, constitute a significant temperament dimension. These traits are strongly linked to psychopathy and serve as predictors of severe, diverse, and enduring antisocial behaviour. Recognizing their clinical importance, callous-unemotional traits have been incorporated as a specifier for Conduct Disorder in the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Research has shown that elevated callous-unemotional traits can manifest independently of significant antisocial behaviour and are often associated with impulse-control disorders, including attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and substance use disorders (Barry, & Sacco, 2016; Waller et al., 2020; Obi-Nwosu, et al., 2019, Onyemaechi, et al., 2022, 2025). Understanding the factors that contribute to the development of these traits is critical for early intervention and prevention. One key area of interest is the role of parenting styles, which are widely recognized as significant predictors of various child outcomes.

Parenting style is a psychological construct that encompasses the standard strategies parents use in child-rearing (Smetana, 2017). Parents play a pivotal role in a child's early development, as their actions and behaviours significantly influence the child's growth from birth (Garrett et al., 2020). Parenting styles are often shaped by a combination of factors, including parental and child temperaments, cultural influences, and the parents' own upbringing. As children develop their own personalities and progress through various life stages, parents may adapt their parenting styles, reflecting both learned behaviours from their own parents and new strategies (Garrett et al., 2020).

Baumrind (1991) defined parenting styles as the consistent patterns in which parents interact with their children across two key dimensions: demandingness and responsiveness. Demandingness

refers to the degree to which parents enforce rules, supervise, and discipline their children, demonstrating a commitment to integrating their children into family expectations and addressing behaviour problems. Responsiveness pertains to the extent to which parents support individuality, self-regulation, and self-assertion by being attuned to and supportive of their children's needs and demands. Mills-Koonce et al., (2016) further elaborated that while demandingness involves parents imposing their views on their children, responsiveness allows for open and reciprocal communication between parents and children.

Baumrind's (1991) framework identified three primary parenting styles: Authoritative, authoritarian and permissive. Authoritative parenting, characterized by warmth, responsiveness, and structure, is generally associated with positive developmental outcomes (Pinquart, 2017). Conversely, authoritarian parenting, which is high in demandingness but low in responsiveness, is linked to negative developmental effects.

Research has shown that harsh and inconsistent discipline, often associated with authoritarian parenting, foster an environment of fear and emotional detachment, contributing to the development of callous-unemotional traits (Azores-Gococo et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2016; Nweke et al., 2019). This type of parenting can hinder the development of empathy and emotional responsiveness in children, increasing the likelihood of callous-unemotional traits (Hawes et al., 2020). Conversely, authoritative parenting, with its balance of warmth and structure, may protect against the development of callous-unemotional traits by promoting secured attachment and emotional regulation (Kochanska et al., 2021).

Permissive parenting, characterized by high responsiveness but low demands, and uninvolved parenting, marked by a lack of both responsiveness and demands, can also influence the development of callous-unemotional traits. Permissive parenting may fail to provide necessary boundaries and guidance, leading to difficulties in self-regulation and an increased risk of externalizing behaviours associated with callous-unemotional traits (Waller et al., 2021). Permissive parenting, with its lack of emotional support and supervision, can result in insufficient socialization experiences crucial for developing empathy and moral reasoning, further increasing the risk of callous-unemotional traits (Clark & Frick, 2018).

Therefore, understanding how various parenting styles—authoritative, authoritarian and permissive affect the development of callous-unemotional (CU) traits among secondary school students. By focusing on this population, the research seeks to identify early predictors of callous-unemotional traits and inform targeted interventions. Knowing these dynamics will help in crafting strategies to reduce the risk of antisocial behaviour and enhance psychosocial outcomes for at-risk students.

Empirical review

Parenting Styles and Callous Unemotional Traits

Zhu, Zou and Li (2024) examined the longitudinal relationship between maternal parenting styles and CU behaviour using Chinese preschoolers as subjects. Through a 1.5-year longitudinal lens, the study probed the relations between maternal parenting styles and CU behaviour in the Chinese

cultural setting. Participants were $N = 492$ Chinese young children (Mage = 52.44 months, SD = 5.00, 48 % girls). At Time 1 (T1), mothers reported their use of authoritative parenting styles (i.e., warmth, reasoning, and autonomy), authoritarian parenting styles (i.e., physical coercion, verbal hostility, and non-reasoning) and children's CU behaviour. At Time 2 (T2; approximately 1.5 years later), mothers again reported the above variables. Results showed that Cross-lagged models indicated that maternal warmth, reasoning, autonomy, and non-reasoning at T1 predicted CU behaviour at T2. However, not only did maternal physical coercion and verbal hostility at T1 predict CU behaviour at T2, but CU behaviour at T1 also predicted maternal physical coercion and verbal hostility at T2. Additionally, there were no gender differences in the relationship between dimensions of maternal parenting styles and CU behaviour.

Prasetiani and Mahanani (2024) evaluated the tendency of Callous-Unemotional (CU) traits in early adolescents based on their perceptions of parental parenting styles, specifically authoritarian, democratic, and permissive. The study employs a comparative method with a cross-sectional design. The sample comprises 236 middle school students in Pati Regency, selected using cluster random sampling. Data were collected using two scales: the Callous Unemotional Traits scale and the Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ), both of which have been validated for reliability. The results indicated significant differences in CU traits among adolescents based on the type of parenting style (p less than 0.05). Adolescents with authoritarian parenting tend to exhibit higher CU traits compared to those with democratic and permissive parenting styles. Democratic parenting generally results in lower CU traits, while permissive parenting shows varied outcomes.

Facci et al. (2024) investigated dimensions of parenting and children's conduct problems and the importance of considering children's callous-unemotional traits. The sample consisted of 136 mothers ($M = 38.09$ years, $SD = 4.51$ years, 45.41% high school degree) with a child (age range 3–5 years) enrolled in kindergarten in central Italy. Multiple regression analyses indicated that, after controlling for level of CP, use of positive reinforcement ($\beta = -0.31$, $p < 0.001$) and warm feelings ($\beta = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$), remained associated with CU traits and punitive parenting was no longer significant. Consistent with predictions, use of positive reinforcement was no longer associated with conduct problems when controlling for CU traits and the positive associations with punitive parenting ($\beta = 0.24$, $p < 0.05$) and negativity ($\beta = 0.36$, $p < 0.001$) remained significant.

Grassetti et al. (2023) tested hypothesized links between callous-unemotional (CU) traits, parenting practices, and disciplinary infractions. Participants were 292 adolescents attending a military-style residential program (M age = 16.76, $SD = 0.731$; 82.9% male; 66.2% White and 33.8% Black). Participants completed the Inventory of Callous-Unemotional Traits (ICU) and the Alabama Parenting Questionnaire (APQ). Disciplinary infractions were accessed via program archival records. Black adolescents reported higher CU traits than did White adolescents and received a higher number of infractions during the program. There were no racial group differences in reports of parenting practices. A Poisson regression that included race suggested that CU traits ($IRR = 1.015$, $p < .001$), negative parenting ($IRR = 1.011$, $p < .001$), and positive parenting ($IRR = 0.995$, $p = .012$) each significantly predicted behavioural infractions in hypothesized directions.

Tomlinson et al. (2022) examined parenting moderates the etiology of callous-unemotional traits in middle childhood. They used twin modeling to estimate additive genetic (A), shared environmental (C), and non-shared environmental (E) influences on CU traits, measured with the Inventory of Callous-Unemotional Traits (ICU) and its subscales. The sample included 600 twin pairs (age 6-11, 230 monozygotic) from neighborhoods with above average levels of family poverty, a risk factor for antisocial behaviour. Tomlinson et al. (2024) also examined the extent to which correlations between parenting, measured via parent- and child-report on the Parental Environment Questionnaire, and CU traits reflected genetic versus environmental factors. Then, they tested whether parenting moderated the heritability of CU traits. Results showed that context of lower-income neighborhoods, CU traits were moderately-to-highly heritable (A=54%) with similar moderate-to-high non-shared environmental influences (E=46%). Bivariate models revealed that associations between CU traits and *warm* parenting were genetic ($r_A=0.22$) and environmental ($r_E=0.19$) in origin, whereas associations between CU traits and *harsh* parenting were largely genetic in origin ($r_A=0.70$). The heritability of CU traits decreased with increasing parental warmth and decreasing harshness.

Goagoses and Schipper (2021) investigated the association between parental warmth/coercion and aggression/rule-breaking behaviour, and to determine whether these associations are mediated by callous-unemotional trait dimensions. A sample of 462 adolescents completed a questionnaire assessing callous-unemotional traits and externalizing behaviour problems, and their parents completed a parenting style questionnaire. A path model revealed that parental warmth had a negative direct effect on the dimension's callousness and uncaring, which in turn had a positive

effect on aggression and rule-breaking behaviour. Parental coercion had a positive direct effect on unemotionality, which was not associated with aggression and rule-breaking behaviour. Only parental warmth had an indirect effect onto externalizing behaviour problems via callous-unemotional traits.

Zhang et al. (2021) investigated pathways from parenting style to CU traits via resting heart rate in a three-year project. Parents of 382 children completed the Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire at Time 1 (children Mean age = 9.06, SD = 0.94, range = 7-11 years), with the heart rate data collected at Time 2 (M = 10.16, SD = 0.93, range = 8-13 years) and CU traits assessed at Time 3 (M = 11.06, SD = 0.94, range = 9-13 years). They found that parenting style and CU traits were associated with resting heart rate, and that structural equation modeling showed resting heart rate to partially mediate the effect of parenting style on CU traits. Specifically, higher levels of authoritarian parenting were associated with lower resting heart rate, which in turn was linked to higher level of CU traits. On the contrary, children in the context of authoritative parenting showed relatively higher resting heart rate, which was predictive of lower CU traits.

Kuay et al. (2021) examined the relations between callous-unemotional traits and perpetration of aggression towards parents in two separate studies, while also considering motivation for aggression and parenting styles experienced among young people. Study 1 involved 60 parents of children aged between 11-17 years old. The online study found high callous-unemotional traits, as reported by parents, to be associated with aggression towards both parents. Both types of motivation (proactive and reactive, as reported by parents) were associated with aggression

towards parents. Study 2 involved 42 youths from an alternative education sample (between 11-16 years old). Youths with higher self-reported callous-unemotional traits reported more aggression towards both parents. Both studies, which had different reporters and different samples, showed youths with higher callous-unemotional traits were more aggressive towards their parents.

Zhong et al. (2020) explored the mediation role of parenting styles (i.e., authoritative and authoritarian) in the relationship between maternal psychopathic traits and child callous-unemotional (CU) traits. A longitudinal research design was adopted using a sample of 486 Chinese mothers and child dyads in which children were between the ages of 8 and 11 years. The data was collected at three time points: mother-reported maternal psychopathy traits at Time One (T1), and parenting at Time 2 (T2), and at Time 3 (T3). Both the mother and the child reported on the child's CU traits. The structural equation modeling (SEM) results revealed that the relation between maternal psychopathic traits and mother-reported child CU traits was fully mediated by maternal authoritarian and authoritative parenting, however, the mediation of maternal authoritarian was on the edge of significance and authoritative parenting was not significant with the child-reported outcome. These findings indicated that maternal psychopathic traits influence child CU traits through authoritarian parenting styles, while the mediation of authoritative parenting styles on child CU traits exists only in mother-reported measures.

Nweke, Dike and Enike (2019) examined parenting styles and callous-unemotional trait as predictors of bullying. Participants in the study were 100 secondary school students from St. John Secondary school and Igwebuikwe grammar school, Awka. Participants comprised of 51 male, and

49 female, with the Age range of 12-19 years, mean age 14.34years and standard deviation 1.99.

Instruments used were parental authority questionnaire developed by Busi (1991), Inventory of callous unemotional trait scale validated by Nwafor (2013) and peer experience questionnaire developed by Hersherger (1999). Multiple regression analysis of variance enter method was used for data management. Result of ANOVA summary showed significant association at $F(3,100) = 16^{**}$, $P < .01$. Furthermore, beta coefficient for Permissive style was $B = .20^{**}$, $P < .01$, Authoritarian style was $B = .40$, $P > .05$, Authoritative style was $B = .25^{**}$, $P < .01$, and Callous-Unemotional trait $B = .23^{**}$, $P < .01$.

Smith (2019) examined the relationships between parenting styles and empathy as well as parenting styles and Callous-Unemotional traits in college students using self-report measures. It was hypothesized that college students with Authoritative parents will score higher on empathy and lower on CU traits than college students with Permissive or Authoritarian parents. Additionally, it was hypothesized that race, sex, and socioeconomic status would moderate these relationships, specifically that the effect of parenting styles on empathy and CU traits would be stronger in college students of minority race, male sex, and low SES. Results suggested that there are relationships between parenting styles, empathy, and CU traits. Namely, Authoritative parenting practices are positively associated with empathy, and Authoritarian parenting practices are negatively associated with CU traits.

METHOD

Participants

The researcher used 286 secondary school students in Awka, Anambra State, comprising 131(45.8%) males and 155(54.2%) females aged from 14 to 18 years with mean age of 15.29 and a standard deviation of 1.46. School data showed that 101 (35.3%) were drawn from Capital City, 68 (23.8%) were drawn from Amaenyi Girls, 32 (11.2%) were drawn from St. John, 37 (12.9%) were drawn from Kenneth Dike Memorial, 37 (12.9%) were drawn from Igwebuikwe Grammar School, and 11 (3.8%) were drawn from Nnamdi Azikiwe High school. Since students in SSS classes were more matured and would better understand the items in the questionnaires, the researcher chooses SSS classes. Nonetheless, simple random sampling method was utilized in selecting one out of the three levels (SSS classes): 139 (48.6%) were drawn from SSS 1, 105 (36.7%) were drawn from SSS 2 and 42 (14.7%) were drawn from SSS 3. thereafter, purposive sampling method were employed to recruit participants who are readily available and willing to participate. This non-probability sampling method allows for easy access to participants (Goodwin, 2013).

Instruments

Instruments used in this study were the parental authority questionnaire which measures parenting styles, inventory of callous-unemotional traits which measures the callous-unemotional traits.

Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ)

The questionnaire was developed by Buri (1991) is designed to measure parental authority, or disciplinary practices, from the point of view of the child (of any age). The scale contained 30

items with 3 dimensions. This scale is arranged in a 5 point likert format ranging from 1=strongly disagree, 2= disagree 3= undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree. Buri (1991) found an alpha of coefficient of 0.77, and test reliability of 0.72. However, Ugwu (2011) revalidated the questionnaire using 30 Nigerian samples from National Grammar School Nike Enugu state. An alpha of coefficient 0.84 and a split half reliability of 0.64 were obtained. Also a concurrent validity of 0.84. $p < .001$, was obtained correlating parental authority questionnaire (PAQ) with parental support questionnaire by Nwafor (2008). In this study, the researcher conducted a pilot test using 15 private senior secondary school students in Awka City and obtained Cronbach alpha of 0.86 for Authoritative parenting style with mean norm of 37.73 and standard deviation of 6.59. For Authoritarian parenting style Cronbach alpha of 0.82 was confirmed and mean norm of 37.13 and standard deviation of 5.58. For Permissive parenting style Cronbach alpha of 0.71 was confirmed and mean norm of 40.60 and standard deviation of 3.18. For the overall scale, the researcher reported Cronbach alpha of 0.92 for parenting style with mean norm of 115.47 and standard deviation of 13.69.

Inventory of Callous-Unemotional traits

This inventory was used to measure lack of empathy. It is a 24 item questionnaire, which was originally developed by Frick, (2004), but was validated by (Essau, 2006 & Kimonis, 2008), after the validation, 22 items were retained. The items are rated on a four (4) point Likert scale format ranging from; 0 -not at all true to 3 -definitely true. The inventory has both direct and indirect scoring style. 12 items are reversed during scoring,(items; 1,2,4,7,11,13,14,15, 17,21,22). The scale is made up of three factors (uncaring, callousness and unemotional). The measure of internal

consistency show a total alpha coefficient of the 22 items to be 0.81, and for the three subscales were 0.81, 0.80 and 0.53 for uncaring, callousness and unemotional, respectively. Nwafor, C.E (2013) revalidated the inventory using Nigerian sample. His internal consistency using the coefficient Cronbach alpha for the total of ICU 22 items was 0.75 and for the three subscales were 0.71, 0.71, and 0.56 for uncaring, callous and unemotional respectively. Construct validity of the ICU showed significant positive correlation with measure of aggression; $r = .24$, $P < 0.01$. The researcher conducted a pilot test using 15 private senior secondary school students in Awka City and obtained Cronbach alpha of 0.88 for Inventory of Callous-Unemotional traits with mean norm of 65.47 and standard deviation of 9.36.

Procedure

The researcher was accompanied by three trained research assistants to the schools to administer the copies of the questionnaires to the students. Consent was obtained from the principals. Due to the students' unfamiliarity with questionnaires, the researchers explained the concept and response pattern, ensuring their understanding and willingness to participate. The questionnaires were administered to available students in their classrooms, who voluntarily agree to participate. The questionnaire administration will take approximately 30 to 45 minutes. Completed questionnaires were collated. However, only students who participated voluntarily were adopted for the study, and the reluctant students were excluded. No remuneration were offered.

Ethically, certain aspects of ethics were employed by the researcher before and during the administration of instruments to avoid variables that are extraneous such as label, bias. First, the

researcher sought the consents of the participants before embarking on the research. The researcher also informed the participants the nature of the research and essence of the study they are about to embark on. This was done to enable the respondents to be open and sincere in their responses. More so, the researcher assured the participants that the result of the test and questionnaire would remain confidential. This is to give the respondents a relaxed state of mind and avoid any thought of labeling that the participants might have.

Design and Statistics

Predictive design was employed for this study and Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected using SPSS 25.0. Predictive research design is a methodological approach aimed at forecasting outcomes based on existing data and trends of the study variables parental styles (independent variable) and callous-unemotional traits (dependent variable). Multiple regression analysis was used for the analysis to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance; this is because multiple regression is the appropriate statistics to test predictions of variables that has dimensions.

RESULT

Table 1: Descriptive and Zero Order Matrix Coefficient Statistics of Parenting Styles (Authoritative, Authoritarian and Permissive) and Callous Unemotional Traits

Variables	Mean	Std. D	1	2	3	4
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1. Callous UE.T.	51.11	2.80	1.00			
2. Authoritative	15.27	2.41	.28**	1.00		
3. Authoritarian	17.67	3.79	-.09	-.16**	1.00	
4. Permissive	15.51	2.66	-.42**	.34**	-.33**	1.00

Result showed that authoritative parenting style had positive relationship with callous unemotional traits at $r(N= 286)$, .28, $p<.05$ (M: 15.27, SD: 2.41). Authoritarian parenting style had no relationship with callous unemotional traits at $r(N= 286)$, -.09, $p>.05$ (M: 17.67, SD: 3.79). Permissive parenting style had negative relationship with callous unemotional traits at $r(N= 286)$, -.42, $p<.05$ (M: 15.51, SD: 2.66).

Summary of Findings

1. Authoritative parenting style positively and significantly predicted callous-unemotional traits.
2. Authoritarian parenting style negatively predicted callous-unemotional traits.
3. Permissive parenting style negatively predicted callous-unemotional traits.

DISCUSSION

The first hypothesis which stated that authoritative parenting style will significantly predict callous-unemotional traits among secondary school students in Awka metropolis, Anambra State was confirmed, because authoritative parenting style predicted callous-unemotional traits. This implies that increase in authoritative parenting style implies increase in callous-unemotional traits. Hence, it can be said from this study that senior secondary school students that were from authoritative parents tend to have high penchant for callous-unemotional traits possibly due to what they observed from their parents as way of living and method of achieving submission and attachment from others. Theoretically, this affirms what Ecologists believe that one cannot and should not separate out the person from the environment; the two are integrally connected. This constant interaction between the two is described as transactional influence. In the case of parent-child relationships, this means that the child's behaviour or characteristics can influence both the parent and the context in which the interactions occur. In turn, the context influences the child's subsequent behaviour and characteristics.

Empirically, this affirmed the findings of Smith (2019) results that suggested that there were relationships between parenting styles, empathy, and CU traits. Namely, authoritative parenting practices are positively associated with empathy. Similarly, the finding supported Nweke, Dike and Enike (2019) result that showed significant association of authoritative style and Callous-Unemotional trait. These observations show that children are biologically influenced by characteristics that interact with multiple levels of the natural environment.

Second hypothesis which stated that authoritarian parenting style will significantly predict callous-unemotional traits among secondary school students in Awka metropolis, Anambra State was accepted due to authoritarian parenting style negatively predicted callous unemotional traits. That means as authoritarian parenting style decreases callous unemotional traits increases. This denotes that decline in parents' use of strict discipline and punishment to control their children have resulted into high levels of children's behavioural control that expresses itself in verbal hostility and physical punishment being witnesses today among secondary school in Anambra State. These irresponsible behaviours in the name of asserting oneself often produce poor social skills, worse academics; reveal the students' low self-efficacy and inferiority complex or insecure attachment. Theoretically, Bowlby (1978) posits that infants need to form a close relationship with at least one primary caregiver to ensure their survival, and to develop healthy social and emotional functioning. Since, insecure attachment has been associated with development of un-healthy traits and behaviours such as callous unemotional traits (Alzeer et al., 2019; Biachi, et.al, 2025; Achebe & Onyemaechi, 2025; Van Der Zouwen et al., 2018).

Empirically, this agrees with Zhang et al. (2021) result that found that parenting style and CU traits were associated with resting heart rate, and that structural equation modeling showed resting heart rate to partially mediate the effect of parenting style on CU traits. Specifically, higher levels of authoritarian parenting were associated with lower resting heart rate, which in turn was linked to higher level of CU traits. More so, it agrees with Goagoses and Schipper (2021) result that revealed that parental warmth had a negative direct effect on the dimensions callousness and uncaring, which in turn had a positive effect on aggression and rule-breaking behaviour, whereas parental

coercion had a positive direct effect on unemotionality, which was not associated with aggression and rule-breaking behaviour. This finding also indicate that students who experience significant strains from parenting styles and view them as unjust may develop heightened levels of anger and resentment. These emotions, coupled with limited coping resources and social support, can lead to behavioural responses that foster callous-unemotional traits, such as a lack of empathy and emotional detachment.

Third hypothesis which stated that permissive parenting style will not significantly predict callous-unemotional traits among secondary school students in Awka metropolis, Anambra State was accepted because permissive parenting style negatively predicted callous unemotional traits. This connotes that decrease in permissive parenting style means increase in callous unemotional traits. This shows that parents trying to have high psychological control over their children do not allow them to make their own rules and decisions. As a result, the children resort to callous unemotional behaviour such as misconduct behaviour and lack of impulse control as a way of resistance to parental and significant others control. Theoretically, this suggested that students with high levels of negative emotionality, low coping skills, and limited social support are more likely to develop CU traits in response to strain.

Empirically, this supports Prasetiani and Mahanani (2024) results that indicated that significant differences in CU traits among adolescents based on the type of parenting style. Adolescents with authoritarian parenting tend to exhibit higher CU traits compared to those with democratic and permissive parenting styles. Democratic parenting generally results in lower CU traits, while

permissive parenting shows varied outcomes. The finding also agrees with Tomlinson et al. (2022)

result that revealed that associations between CU traits and warm parenting were genetic and environmental in origin, whereas associations between CU traits and harsh parenting were largely genetic in origin. The heritability of CU traits decreased with increasing parental warmth and decreasing harshness. That means parents investment in their children's "human capital" especially by investing in their education, health, time, good neighbors and other "input" can improve children future well-being and reduce callous unemotional traits.

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